

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
CLOTHS STORE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM
PROJECT
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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the Clothes store management system is to use the existing manual systems with the help of computer equipment and complete computer software to meet their expectations that their valuable data/information is archived for a longer period of time with easy access and manipulation. The necessary software and hardware are readily available and easy to use.

The clothing store management system described above can result in an error free, safe, reliable and fast management system. This can help the user focus on other activities rather than record keeping. Therefore, the system will help the organization to make better use of their resources. The organization can maintain IT records without redundant entries.

This means that you don't have to be distracted by irrelevant information and still reach the top. The goal is to automate their existing manual system with computer equipment and full computer software to meet their needs, allowing them to store valuable data/information for a longer period of time with easy access and manipulation. The project describes how to manage to achieve good performance and better customer service.

Introduction

The “Cloth store Management System” was developed to overcome the problems that prevail in the practical manual system. This software is supported to eliminate and, in some cases, reduce the difficulties encountered by this legacy system. Furthermore, this system is designed for the specific business needs to be implemented.

Smooth and efficient operation. The application is minimized to avoid data entry errors. It also provides an error message if invalid data is entered. No formal knowledge is required for the use of this system by the user. So all of this proves that it is easy to use. The clothing store management system described above can result in an error free, safe, reliable and fast management system. It can help you focus on other tasks instead of focusing on keeping records. Big or small, every business faces challenges and manages information on products, apparel, businesses, payments, and inventory.

Each clothing store management system has different clothing requirements; that’s how we design unique employee management systems, tailored to your management needs. This is intended to support strategic planning and help ensure your organization is equipped with the right information and details for your future goals. Plus, for busy executives who are always on the go, our systems are equipped with remote access capabilities so you can manage your workforce anytime, anywhere. This proposed system ultimately allows you to better manage the resources and time of an organization.

Purpose

The Software Requirements Specification (SRS) provides a detailed description of the requirements for the apparel store management system. This SRS allows for a complete understanding of what to expect from the MSMS to be built. A clear understanding of the tissue management system and its capabilities helps develop the appropriate software for the end user. It will be used for the development of the future phases of the project.

This SRS serves as the basis for the project. From this SRS the system can be designed, built and finally tested. This SRS is used by the software developers who create the system and by the end users of the clothing store. Software engineers will use SRS to fully understand the expectations of this apparel store management system to create the appropriate software. End users of clothing stores can use this SRS as a “test” to see if the software engineers will build the system as they expect. If it does not meet their expectations, end users can indicate how it does not meet their expectations and the software engineers modify the SRS to meet the needs of the end users.

Project Scope of Cloth Store Management System

It can help you to collect perfect management in detail. The collection will be clear, meaningful, and simple in no time. It will help a person to fully and clearly see the direction of the passing year. It also helps with all the ongoing work related to the clothing store management system. In addition, collection costs will be reduced, and administration and the collection process will run smoothly.

Our project is aimed at the automation of business processes, i.e. we have tried

- To computerize various processes of the management system of clothing stores.
- In a computer system, the person has to fill in multiple forms and the number of copies of the forms can easily be generated at the same time.
- It is not necessary to create the manifest in a computer system, but we can do it directly. Print it, which saves us time.
- Helping employees understand the efforts made in their respective areas of work.
- Use resources efficiently by increasing their productivity through automation purposes.
- Meet user requirements to allow users and operators to be easily understood
- It must be easy to use,
- Have an exemplary and scalable database

Cloth Store Management System Modules:

- **Fabric Management Module:** Used to manage fabric details.
- **Inventory module:** to manage inventory and payment details
- **Product management module:** used to manage product information and details.
- **Product type form:** used to manage product type details
- Company form
- **Login form:** used to manage credentials used to manage system users
- User form and components
- Easy creation and editing of problems
- List of query issues at any depth and more comprehensive reports and graphs
- User Accounts to Control Access and Maintain Security Status and Simple Solutions
- Multi-level priority and severity.
- Goals and milestones to guide programmers
- Robust database
- Different levels of reports available with many filter criteria
- Includes better storage capacity and Accuracy in work
- Quick and easy retrieval of information Well-designed reports

Software Specification Requirements

The software requirements specification is created after the software analysis task as part of the function engineering and performance attributed to the detailed description of the function and behavior, an indication of the performance requirements and design constraints, appropriate validation criteria, and other data relevant to the requirement.

- The proposed system has the following requirements:
- The system must store information about the new garment.
- The system is designed to help internal staff stay informed about the product and

find it based on various questions.

- The system must keep a record of quantity.
- The system must keep a record of the product type.
- The system should update and delete the record.
- The system also needs a search field.

Software Requirements:

- **Operating system:** Windows 98, Windows XP, Windows 7, Linux
- **Language:** PHP runtime environment
- **Database:** MySQL
- **Browser:** Opera, Chrome, etc.
- **Web Server:** Apache
- **Software Development Kit** PHP
- **Scripting Language Enable** [JavaScript](#)
- **Driver:** MySQL Connector

Hardware

- **PROCESSOR:** Pentium III or higher
- **RAM:** 128 GB
- **HARD DISK:** 20 GB
- **MONITOR:** 15-inch color monito

Functional Requirements

Functional requirements define basic actions that the system must execute. The applicable requirements for the system are divided into three main categories: Apparel Inventory, Customer and Billing Information, and Sales and Supplier Information. See use cases for more details.

- Stock of clothing
- The system records the stock of clothing.
- The system needs to be updated when new stock arrives.
- The system must report the inventory of expired drugs.
- The system records drug details,
- customer information, and billing
- The system displays the customer information.
- The system creates the invoice.
- The system must store customer information.
- The system records the billing.
- Sales and Suppliers
- The system displays and updates supplier information from time to time.
- The system should display the number of sales with a profit and loss record.

Non-Functional Requirements

Functional requirements define performance requirements, database logic requirements, design constraints, standards compliance, reliability, availability, security, maintainability, and portability.

Performance Requirements

It defines acceptable response times for the system functionality.

- The UI screens should take ten seconds to load.
- Credentials must be verified within five seconds.
- Queries must return results within five seconds.

Class Diagram:

Within a technique, the class diagram has become very central. Virtually every technique has included a variation of that technique. The class diagram is subject to even the most fantastic modeling concepts. Although everyone needs the essentials, advanced concepts are used less often. A class diagram describes the types of objects in the system and the different types of static relationships that exist between them. There are two main types of fixed relationships:

- Association
- Subtype

The class diagram also shows the attributes and operations of a class and the constraints that apply to how objects are linked

Project Use Case Module

The use case model for each system consists of “use cases”. Use cases represent how the user can use the system. An easy way To find all use cases for a system is to ask the question “What can the user do with the system?” Use cases mean breaking down system behavior into transactions so that each transaction performs a specific practical action from the user’s perspective.

The purpose of the use case is to define consistent behavior without exposing the internal structure of the system. A use case generally represents a sequence of interactions between the user and the project. These interactions consist of a mainline that describes the regular interaction between the user and the system. The use case model represents an artifact of critical analysis and design (activity). Usage can be represented by drawing a use case diagram and writing accompanying text that augments the design.

Data Flow Diagram:

The data flow diagram is the starting point of the design phase,

The requirement specification is functionally decomposed. A DFD is made up of a series of

bubbles connected by lines. The bubbles represent the data transformation and the lines represent the data flow in the system. A DFD describes the data flow and not how it is processed, so it does not contain hardware, software, and data structure.

A data flow diagram (DFD) is a graphical representation of the “flow” of data or information through the system. DFDs can also be used to visualize data processing (structured design). A data flow diagram (DFD) is a powerful modeling technique for analyzing and building information processes. DFD stands for an illustration that explains the flow or movement of information in a circle. DFD maps this information flow into an input-output approach. A DFD can be called a process model.

The data flow diagram is a graphical description of a system’s data and how the data will be interpreted by the user.

Entity Relations Model

ER model is a popular conceptual high-level data model. This model and its variants are commonly used in the conceptual design of database applications, and many database design tools use this concept. A database that confirms an ER diagram can be represented by a collection of tables in the relational system. The mapping from the ER diagram to the entities is:

- Attributes
- Relationships

Limitations of The Garment Management System

Although I have tried my best to make the software flexible and easy to use I cannot rule out limitations either. While the software offers its users a wide range of options, some complex options cannot be covered, partly due to logistics and partly due to a lack of sophistication. Lack of time was also a major obstacle. Therefore, it was not possible to make the software infallible and dynamic. Lack of time also made me skip some parts like saving old candidate results etc.

Numerous efforts have resulted in the software being easy to use even for non-IT people. However, it is recognized that at first, this can be somewhat problematic for a layman. The user receives assistance at every stage for his convenience while using the software.

Source code

```
#include<fstream.h>
#include<conio.h>
#include<string.h>
#include<stdio.h>

class dress{
private:
char filename[20]; protected:

char dressname[60];
char dressid[10]; float
price;
void get();
};

void dress::get()
{
cout<<"\n ENTER DRESS NAME : ";
cin>>dressname;
cout<<"\n ENTER DRESS ID NO : ";
cin>>dressid;
cout<<"\n ENTER DRESS PRICE : ";
cin>>price;

strcpy(filename,dressid);
strcat(filename,".txt");
ofstream x(filename);

x<<"\n\nDRESS NAME :"<<dressname;
x<<"\n\nDRESS ID :"<<dressid;
x<<"\n\nPRICE :"<<price;
x.close();

}

class male:protected dress
{
public:
male();
};
```

```

void male::male()
{
    get();
    fstream x("MALE.txt",ios::app|ios::out);
    x<<dressname;
    x<<"\t"<<dressid;
    x<<"\t "<<price<<endl;
    x.close();
}

class female:protected dress{

    public:
        female();

};

void female::female()
{
    get();
    fstream x("FEMALE.txt",ios::app|ios::out);
    x<<dressname;
    x<<"\t"<<dressid;
    x<<"\t "<<price<<endl;
    x.close();
}

class childrn:protected dress

{

    public:
        childrn();

};

void childrn::childrn()
{
    get();
    fstream x("CHILD.txt",ios::app|ios::out);
    x<<dressname;
    x<<"\t"<<dressid;
    x<<"\t "<<price<<endl;
    x.close();
}

```

```

class add {
    private:
        int i;
    public:
        add();
};

add::add()
{
    clrscr();

    while(1)
    {
        clrscr();
        cout<<"\n\n";
        cout<<"\t\t Categories of the dress products\n\n";
        cout<<"\n\n01. MALE. \n\n02. FEMALE. \n\n03. CHILDREN OR";
        cout<<"\n\n04. EXIT. ";
        cout<<"\n\n\n\t Enter your option :";
        cin>>i;

        if(i==1)
        {
            male m;
        }

        if(i==2)
        {
            female f;
        }

        if(i==3)
        {
            childrn c;
        }
        if(i==4)

break;
    }
}

```

```
}  
}
```

```
class search{
```

```
    private: int m;
```

```
    char ch;
```

```
public:
```

```
    search();
```

```
};
```

```
search::search(){
```

```
    while(1)
```

```
    {
```

```
        clrscr();
```

```
        cout<<"\n\n 01.Male"; cout<<"\n\n
```

```
02.Female"; cout<<"\n\n
```

```
03.Children"; cout<<"\n\n
```

```
04.Search by id"; cout<<"\n\n
```

```
05.Exit"; cout<<"\n\n\t Select an
```

```
option :";cin>>m;
```

```
        if(m==1)
```

```
        {
```

```
            ifstream m("MALE.txt");
```

```
            while(m)
```

```
            {
```

```
                m.get(ch);
```

```
                cout<<ch;
```

```
            }
```

```

    getch();
    }

    if(m==2)
    {
        ifstream m("FEMALE.txt");

        while(m)
        {
            m.get(ch);
            cout<<ch;

        }
        getch();
    }

    if(m==3)
    {
        ifstream m("CHILD.txt");
        while(m)
        {
            m.get(ch);
            cout<<ch;

        }
        getch();
    }

    if(m==4)
    {
        char id[10],filename[20];

        cout<<"input id for search:";
        cin>>id;
        strcpy(filename,id);
        strcat(filename,".txt");
    }

```

```

        ifstream m(filename);

        while(m)
            {
                m.get(ch);
                cout<<ch;
            }

        getch();
    }

    if(m==5)
        break;

    }

}

class cut{
public:
    cut();

};

cut::cut()
{
    char id[20],filename[20];
    cout<<"\n\nEnter the id to delete : ";
    cin>>id;
    strcpy(filename,id);
    strcat(filename,".txt"); fstream
    x(filename,ios::out);
    x<<"INFORMATION IS UNAVAILABLE";
    x.close();
}

int main()

{
    int i;

```

```
textcolor(5);
textbackground(0);

clrscr();

while(1)

    {
    clrscr();
    cout<< "Choose an option\n\n";
    cout<< "\n\t01. Add a product.\n";
    cout<< "\n\t02. Search any product.\n";
    cout<< "\n\t03. Delete any product.\n";
    cout<< "\n\t04. Exit.";
    cout<< "\n\nEnter an option :";
    cin>>i;

    if(i==1)
        {
        add a;
        }

    if(i==2)
    {

        search s;

    }

    if(i==3)
    {
        cut c;
    }

    if(i==4)
    break;

    }

return 0;

}
```

Output

```
F:\Code Projects Files\NEWW C Projects 19nov\Clothing store mgmt\prod.exe
Clothing Store Management System
Enter [1] To Add Items
Enter [2] To Delete Items
Enter [3] To Search Items
Enter [4] To View Items
Enter [5] To Edit Items
Enter [6] To Calculate Bill
Enter [7] To Exit!
Enter your choice[1-6]
```

TESTING

Testing is an investigation to provide clients with information about the quality of the product. Testing method can be implemented at each phase in the development process, however the most test effort is employed after the requirements have been defined and coding process has been completed.

Conclusion:

To carry out the various user-friendly coding has also been adopted This package will prove influential when it comes to meeting all of the school's needs. The purpose of software planning is to provide the manager with a framework in which reasonable estimates should be made within a limited time frame at the start of the software project and updated periodically as the project progresses.

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